

1 **Sex-specific probing behaviour of the carrot psyllid *Bactericera trigonica* and its**
2 **implication in the transmission of ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*’**

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21 **Abstract**

22 ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum* (Lso)’ is a pathogen of *Solanaceae* but also causes
23 serious physiological disorders in carrots and celery (*Apiaceae*). In carrots, this pathogen is
24 transmitted by the psyllids *Bactericera trigonica* and *Trioza apicalis*. How vector sex
25 influences Lso transmission has not been yet elucidated. Here we report the probing
26 behaviours of male and female *B. trigonica* and their impact on Lso titre transmitted,
27 percentage of transmission, and symptoms produced on carrots when Lso is transmitted by
28 males or females of *B. trigonica*. Vector sex affected the inoculation of Lso; our results
29 suggest that females might inoculate higher Lso titres than males. However, the percentage
30 of transmission was not affected by vector sex at a density of one or eight psyllids per plant.
31 The number of yellow leaves and root weight were not different when Lso was transmitted
32 by males or females at either of the psyllid densities tested, except for groups of females
33 whose Lso transmission resulted in a higher number of yellow leaves than did Lso
34 transmitted by groups of males. Electrical penetration graphs (EPG) showed that the
35 proportion of individuals who reached phloem tissues was similar for males and females.
36 However, EPGs also showed that females probed more times, ingested longer from phloem
37 sieve elements and reached phloem tissues more frequently than did males during an 8-h
38 inoculation access period (IAP). Our study shows that differences in probing behaviours
39 between males and females of *B. trigonica* could modulate how Lso is inoculated by
40 psyllids. These results highlight the importance of taking sex into consideration in psyllid
41 studies of probing behaviour and bacterial transmission.

43 **Introduction**

44 *Candidatus* *Liberibacter solanacearum* (Lso) is a phloem-limited plant pathogenic
45 bacterium transmitted by psyllids (Hemiptera: Psylloidea). On potatoes, Lso has been
46 associated with a vegetative disorder called zebra chip (Liefting et al. 2008a; Abad et al.
47 2009). This disorder causes millions of dollars in losses to the potato industry in North and
48 Central America as well as in New Zealand (Liefting et al. 2008a; Munyaneza 2012;
49 2015a). In addition to potatoes, Lso also infects tomatoes, peppers, tamarillos and other
50 economically important solanaceous plants (Liefting et al. 2008b; 2009). The American
51 potato psyllid, *Bactericera cockerelli*, is the known vector of Lso in solanaceous plants
52 (Munyaneza et al. 2007; Secor et al. 2009).

53 In Europe, Lso was first described in 2010, causing vegetative disorders in carrots in
54 Finland and other Scandinavian countries (Munyaneza et al. 2010a; Nissinen et al. 2014).
55 Recently, Lso has also caused severe carrot crop losses in several locations in the
56 Mediterranean as well as in Germany (Alfaro-Fernandez et al. 2012; Teresani et al. 2014;
57 Loiseau et al. 2014; Tahzima et al. 2014; Munyaneza et al. 2015b). Two different psyllid
58 species have been reported so far as vectors of Lso in carrots: *Trioza apicalis* in northern
59 Europe (Munyaneza et al. 2010b, Nissinen et al. 2014; Munyaneza et al. 2015b) and
60 *Bactericera trigonica* in the Mediterranean region (Alfaro-Fernandez et al. 2012). Due to
61 the recent emergence of the bacterium, the mechanism by which carrot psyllids transmit
62 Lso is not completely understood.

63

64 Lso is transmitted in a propagative-circulative manner. It is acquired by its vector while
65 ingesting from phloem sieve elements of an infected plant and needs to replicate in the
66 vector body. Once Lso reaches the vector's salivary glands it can be inoculated into the
67 phloem sieve tubes of a healthy plant during short periods of salivation (Sandanyaka et al.
68 2014; Mustafa et al. 2015; Cicero et al. 2016). Under this scenario, vector salivation and
69 sap ingestion into the phloem sieve tubes are an absolute prerequisite for pathogen
70 transmission.

71 Vector sex has been reported to influence the probing behaviour of the Asian citrus psyllid
72 *Diaphorina citri* (Serikawa 2011). It is not known if such sex based behavioural differences
73 are present in all psyllid species, nor is it clear how this could impact pathogen
74 transmission. Interestingly, it has been reported that Lso infections in carrots, when
75 mediated by females of the psyllid *T. apicalis*, produced more severe root damage than
76 infections mediated by males (Nissinen et al. 2014). The reasons for such differences
77 remain unexplained. However, it has been hypothesized that differences in the observed
78 symptom severity could be the result of higher Lso titre inoculated due to an increased
79 salivation time by females (Nissinen et al. 2014). Despite its importance, the connection
80 between variation in the probing behaviour of carrot psyllids and Lso delivery into the plant
81 remains unclear. More specifically, whether there is a sex difference in probing behaviour
82 of the Mediterranean carrot psyllid (*B. trigonica*), similar to that reported for *T. apicalis* in
83 Northern Europe, is also unknown. This study aimed to help fill this knowledge gap by
84 investigating the probing behaviour of both female and male *B. trigonica* when transmitting
85 Lso in carrots. Using the DC Electrical Penetration Graph (EPG) technique (Tjallingii
86 1985), we monitored stylet penetration activities of *B. trigonica* and quantified Lso titre

87 inoculated by each sex in carrots using real-time PCR. Finally, symptoms shown by carrot
88 plants when males and females transmitted Lso were compared.

89 **Methods**

90 **Plant and Insect Material**

91 Seeds of carrot (*Daucus carota* cv Bangor) (Bejo Zanden b. v. The Netherlands) were
92 germinated in petri dishes in the dark at 24° C for four days. Carrot seedlings were then
93 individually grown in 8-cm diameter and 18-cm height plastic pots using a mixture of equal
94 parts of vermiculite (No. 3, Asfaltex S.A., Barcelona, Spain) and soil substrate (Kekilla
95 Iberica, Almería, Spain). Batches of seeds and seedlings used for experiments tested
96 negative for *Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum* (Lso) as determined by real-time PCR
97 according to Bertolini et al. (2015). Plants were maintained in a growth chamber with the
98 following conditions: temperature 24:20° C (L:D), photoperiod of 16:8 h (L:D). Plants
99 were watered three times a week and a nutritional complex 20-20-20 (N:P:K) of Nutrichem
100 60 fertilizer (Miller Chemical & Fertilizer Corp., PA, USA) was added once a week to
101 irrigation water at 0.25 g/L. For transmission experiments, 1-leaf stage carrot plants were
102 transferred to greenhouse conditions inside insect proof cages.

103 A *Bactericera trigonica* Lso-infected colony was established from samples kindly supplied
104 by Estrella Hernandez (Instituto Canario de Investigaciones Agrarias (ICIA), Tenerife,
105 Spain), obtained from a population collected from commercial carrot fields in Tenerife in
106 2012. Psyllids were maintained on carrot plants in 47.5 x 47.5 x 47.5 cm (length x width x
107 height) (nylon mesh 150 µm) insect cages at greenhouse conditions. Greenhouse conditions
108 were 28:18° C temperature (L:D) and a photoperiod of 10:14 h (L:D). The psyllid colony

109 was periodically tested using real-time PCR, and the percentage of Lso-infected psyllids
110 was always above 98 %.

111 **Transmission of Lso by males and females.**

112 The Lso percentage of transmission by males and females was compared using two
113 different inoculation access periods (IAP) and psyllid densities. Further, the symptoms
114 caused by Lso to carrot plants when transmitted by both males and females were also
115 compared. In the first set of transmission experiments, an IAP of six hours and eight
116 psyllids per test plant were used. Groups of psyllids were collected from the Lso-infected
117 colony cages with a handmade vacuum aspirator 24 h before conducting transmission
118 assays. Individuals were anesthetized with CO₂ for 4 s in order to be able to separate males
119 and females. All males and females were separated and transferred to different cages
120 containing two carrot plants each and kept under greenhouse conditions. Groups of eight
121 individuals from each sex were collected and placed in Eppendorf tubes just before the
122 transmission test was conducted. Each group of 8 psyllids was released onto a 1-leaf stage
123 carrot receptor seedling by opening and inserting the Eppendorf tube into the soil next to
124 the carrot plant, which was then enclosed in a transparent plastic cylindrical cage following
125 a procedure similar to the one described by Nissinen et al. (2012). Psyllids started to leave
126 the Eppendorf almost immediately after opening the lid and were able to access and remain
127 on the test plant for 6-h IAP. There were three different treatments: i) 20 carrot plants
128 exposed to groups of eight males; ii) 20 carrot plants exposed to groups of eight females;
129 and iii) 20 plants that served as negative controls (carrot plants that were never exposed to
130 psyllid probing). This assay was repeated three times, and treatments were arranged in a
131 completely randomized design.

132 For the second set of transmission experiments, the methodology was similar to that
133 described above, but just one psyllid was released for an IAP of 8 h on the receptor plant. In
134 this case, the number of replicates was also three, but 30 plants were used for each
135 treatment. This assay was also repeated three times and plants were arranged in completely
136 randomized design. In this assay, we shifted the IAP from six to eight h to increase the
137 chances of Lso transmission, as the psyllid number was decreased from eight to one.

138 For both sets of experiments, psyllids were removed from the receptor plants at the end of
139 the IAP and were tested to confirm the presence of Lso by real-time PCR (insects were
140 individually tested in the one psyllid assay and pooled in groups of eight in the eight psyllid
141 assay). Test plants were sprayed with 1 g L⁻¹ of Confidor ® (Bayer, Kansas City MO
142 USA). A second insecticide spray was repeated 10 d later to ensure that possible nymphs
143 were removed. Symptom development was monitored for 60 d post inoculation; then plants
144 were collected and the number of yellow leaves and root weight were quantified. Leaf
145 samples were also taken to perform real-time PCR for detection of Lso.

146 **Lso detection by real-time PCR.**

147 DNA was purified for each plant and insect used in the experiment. A crude plant extract
148 was obtained by grinding 0.6 g of symptomatic plant material (leaves) in 4 ml of extraction
149 buffer. Crude plant extract was stored at -20 °C until use. DNA purification from 200 ml of
150 crude extract was performed following the CTAB (cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide)
151 protocol (Murray & Thomson 1980). For Lso detection on psyllids, individual insects were
152 squashed onto Whatman 3MM paper using the round bottom of an Eppendorf tube (Olmos
153 et al. 1996; Bertolini et al. 2014). Whatman paper containing the sample was placed inside
154 an Eppendorf tube and 100 µl of triton 100X were added. Then, tubes were placed in

155 boiling water at 100 °C for 10 min to allow the release of the DNA from the paper to the
156 triton.

157 Lso was detected by real-time PCR according to Bertolini et al. (2015) for both plant and
158 insect samples, using universal primers for Liberibacters, CaLsppF (5'-
159 GCAGGCCTAACACATGCAAGT-3') and CaLsppR (5'-
160 GCACACGTTTCCATGCGTTAT-3'), and a '*Ca. L. solanacearum*'-specific TaqMan
161 probe (5' FAM-AGCGCTTATTTTAAATAGGAGCGGCAGACG-3' TAMRA). An
162 Applied Biosystems 7300 thermal cycler was used; PCR conditions were as follows: an
163 initial step of 95 °C for 10 min followed by 45 cycles of 95 °C for 15 s and 60 °C for 1 min.

164 **Quantification of bacterial titre inoculated by males or females.**

165 The bacterial titre inoculated by a single male or female in a receptor plant was quantified
166 by quantitative real-time PCR in an independent assay. Single Lso-infected psyllids (male
167 or females) were placed on one leaflet of a one-leaf age Lso-free carrot plant and enclosed
168 on a restricted area (0.5 cm diameter) by using a small clip cage. After an IAP of 8 h,
169 psyllids were removed from the leaflet and processed for quantification of Lso by real-time
170 PCR as described above. A total of 90 test plants (50 for males and 40 for females) were
171 used in this experiment. The restricted area of the leaflet where the psyllid was probing was
172 cut from the test plant with a lid of an Eppendorf tube after the psyllid was removed from
173 the receptor plant. Leaf disks of each plant were sampled and processed for real-time PCR
174 as described previously. Samples that were PCR-negative were discarded from the analysis.
175 To establish the standard curve for real-time PCR, plasmid DNA was kindly provided by
176 Dr Mariano Cambra from Instituto Valenciano de Investigaciones Agrarias (IVIA).

177 Valencia, Spain). Avogadro's constant was used to estimate the number of plasmid DNA
178 copies. Then, eight 10-fold plasmid dilution series were obtained that ranged from 1.3×10^8
179 to 1.3 ng/ml according to Bertolini et al. (2015).

180 **Comparison of the probing behaviours of males and females.**

181 The probing behaviour of Lso-infected *B. trigonica* males and females was compared by
182 analysis of different EPG variables. Twenty EPG recordings were conducted on different
183 carrot plants (one plant for each insect) and for each of the two treatments (either males or
184 females). EPG recordings were obtained using a 4-channel DC EPG system (type Giga-4,
185 Wageningen University, The Netherlands). Young adult Lso infected psyllids, 8 d of age,
186 were collected from the insect rearing colonies and placed individually inside an Eppendorf
187 tube. Psyllids were anesthetized with CO₂ for 4 s, divided by sex and then immobilized
188 using a vacuum-operated plate (Eyela Aspirator A3S, Tokyo Rikakikai 6 Co.LTD, Japón)
189 under a dissecting microscope. A thin gold wire (diameter 18µm) (Coining ,Montvale, NY
190 USA) was placed on the psyllid mesothorax and glued by a small drop of conductive water-
191 based silver glue solution (EPG Systems, Wageningen. The Netherlands). The opposite end
192 of the gold wire was attached to a copper electrode (input electrode). Then the attached
193 insect was placed on the abaxial surface of a fully expanded carrot leaf. Another electrode
194 (copper, 10 cm long, 2 mm wide) was inserted in the substrate of the pot containing the
195 carrot plant to complete the electrical circuit. Prior to EPG all plants used tested negative
196 for Lso by real-time PCR. The monitoring system (plant, insect and amplifier) was placed
197 inside a Faraday cage to avoid external electrical noise. Each insect was monitored for 8 h
198 under laboratory conditions (22-24°C) starting immediately after insects were placed on the
199 leaf. Data were analysed using Stylet+ software for Windows (EPG Systems, Wageningen,

200 The Netherlands). EPG waveforms previously described for psyllids (Bonani et al. 2010;
201 Civolani et al. 2011; Pearson et al. 2014), were identified as follows: non-probing (np),
202 intercellular stylet pathway (C), initial contact with phloem tissue (D), salivation into
203 phloem sieve elements (E1), passive phloem sap uptake from the phloem sieve elements
204 (E2) and active intake of xylem sap from xylem elements (G). The behavioural data was
205 compiled using the MS Excel Workbook for automatic EPG data compilation developed by
206 Sarriá et al. (2009). Selected EPG variables (mean \pm SE) (listed in Online resource 1) were
207 calculated using the SPSS statistical package. The following variables were calculated as
208 described in Backus et al. (2007): PPW, proportion of individuals that produced a specific
209 waveform type; NWEI, number of waveform events per insect, that is the sum of the
210 number of events of a particular waveform divided by the total number of insects under
211 each treatment; NPI, number of probes per insect (the number of stylet insertions into the
212 plan tissue regardless of the activity performed); WDI, total waveform duration (min)
213 (TWD) per insect (that is the sum of durations of each event of a particular waveform)
214 divided by the total number of insects under each treatment; and WDE, total waveform
215 duration (min) per event (that is the sum of the duration of the events for a particular
216 waveform) divided by the total number of events of that particular waveform under each
217 treatment. We calculated also WDEI (mean waveform duration per event per insect) for the
218 waveforms related to phloem activities (E1 and E2) because they are associated to the
219 transmission of Lso.

220 **Statistical analysis**

221 Pairwise comparisons between the Lso percentage of transmission under the different
222 treatments were analysed using a chi-square test and by Fisher's exact test when expected

223 values were lower than 5 cases. Root weight and number of yellow leaves obtained from
224 plants inoculated by either Lso-infected males or females were compared by means of a
225 one-way ANOVA followed by pairwise comparisons for least significant differences
226 (LSD). If data did not follow the ANOVA assumptions, a Kruskal-Wallis test was
227 performed followed by a Mann-Whitney test on each pair of groups, adjusting P values
228 with the Bonferroni method. An adjusted general linear model was carried out to compare
229 the concentration of Lso inoculated in carrot leaves by males or females. Concentration of
230 Lso in psyllid bodies was handled as a fixed factor and divided in tertiles ($n=11$) with three
231 different levels (low, medium and high). Comparisons between probing behaviour of males
232 and females were made using a Student's t -test for Gaussian variables or a Mann-Whitney
233 U test when normality was not achieved. Data were previously transformed with $\sqrt{(x + 0.5)}$
234 or $\ln(x + 1)$ if needed to reduce heteroscedasticity and achieve normality. All data were
235 processed with the statistical software SPSS 21 (SPSS 2013).

236 **Results**

237 **Transmission of Lso by males or females.**

238 None of the uninfected control plants tested positive for Lso. Transmission experiments
239 showed that there were no significant ($P>0.05$) differences in the percentage of
240 transmission of Lso between the two sexes of *B. trigonica* when testing different number of
241 insects per test plant and different IAP (Fig. 1). When assays were performed using a
242 psyllid density of eight individuals per plant and an IAP of 6 h, Lso percentages of
243 transmission for both sexes were similar (81.66 ± 7.26 (49/60) for males and 80.00 ± 12.58
244 (48/60) for females) ($\chi^2=0.03$, $df=1$, $P=0.85$) (Fig. 1).

245 For the second transmission assay, a single psyllid per test plant and an IAP of 8 h were
246 used. The results again demonstrated no differences in the percentage of transmission
247 between sexes, although efficacy decreased as expected (23.33 ± 6.65 (21/90) for males and
248 20.00 ± 5.23 (18/90) for females) ($\chi^2=0.46$, $df=1$, $P=0.49$) (Fig. 1).

249 **Symptoms caused by Lso when inoculated by males or females.**

250 None of the control plants showed symptoms. However, all plants positive for Lso showed
251 stunting of roots and shoots and leaf yellowing 60 d post inoculation. Root weight of the
252 male- and female-inoculated carrot plants was reduced by almost half compared to the
253 healthy control plant for one and eight psyllids (Table 1). However, there were no
254 differences in root weight between male and female-inoculated carrots, and results were
255 similar for the two psyllid densities used ($P>0.05$) (Table 1).

256 Interestingly, when the numbers of yellow leaves were compared, differences between all
257 treatments were found when eight individuals per plant were used (Table 1). Female-
258 inoculated carrots showed a higher number of yellow leaves when compared with male-
259 inoculated carrots (Table 1). On the other hand, when a psyllid density of one was used, the
260 number of yellow leaves was not significantly different between carrots inoculated by
261 males or females (Table 1).

262 **Bacterial titre inoculated by males and females.**

263 Real-time PCR indicated that the Lso titre in psyllid body was higher for males than for
264 females (number of Lso amplified targets per psyllid: $557,135.48 \pm 260,237$ in males and
265 $155,882.48 \pm 62,172$ in females, $t=2.26$, $df=1$, $P=0.03$), however the overall Lso titre
266 inoculated was similar between sexes ($F=5.35$, $df=2$, 31 , $P=0.10$) (Table 2) (Fig. 2).

267 Interestingly, our data showed that Lso titre inoculated in carrot leaves was statistically
268 affected by psyllid titre ($F=13.93$, $df=2$, 31 $P < 0.0001$) and there was also a significant
269 interaction between sex and psyllid titre ($F=5.35$, $df=2$, 31 , $P=0.01$) (Table 2) (Fig. 2).
270 Thus, females with high Lso titres inoculated significantly more bacteria compare to males
271 in the same category (Table 2), (Fig. 2) (online resource 2), suggesting that females with
272 high Lso titres were more efficient inoculators than males.

273 **Probing behaviour of males and females.**

274 Analysed sequential variables were not significantly different between males and females.
275 The analysis of non-sequential EPG variables demonstrated that females (NPI: $16.85 \pm$
276 1.60) probed more frequently than males (NPI: 11.45 ± 1.71) ($t=0.74$, $df=1$, $P=0.04$). The
277 duration of non-probing events was longer for males (WDE: 17.29 ± 2.37 minutes) than for
278 females (WDE: 10.07 ± 1.44 minutes) ($U=33607.50$, $df=1$, $P=0.01$) (Online resource 3).
279 Males also showed a higher proportion of xylem activities than females. While waveform G
280 (PPW) was present in all recordings for males, only 15/20 (75%) of females performed this
281 waveform ($\chi^2=5.71$, $df=1$, $P=0.01$). NWEI mean values for G were also significantly higher
282 for males (1.45 ± 0.13) compared to female values (1.00 ± 0.17) ($U= 132.00$, $df=1$, $P=0.03$)
283 (Online resource 3). In our EPG recordings, phloem salivation (E1) and phloem ingestion
284 (E2) frequently alternate in the same probe. As a result, the mean number of E1 per insect
285 (NWEI) could not be used to accurately describe frequency of phloem contacts within a
286 single probe. Therefore, we used the number of E1 at the beginning of each phloem probe
287 (Initial E1) to describe frequency of phloem contacts that could lead to inoculation of Lso.
288 Data showed that initial E1 numbers were significantly higher for females than for males
289 (NWEI: 0.50 ± 0.18 for males and 1.65 ± 0.39 for females) ($U=117.50$, $df=1$, $P=0.01$) (Fig.

290 3a). Also waveform D numbers were higher for females than for males (NWEI: 1.70 ± 0.40
291 for females and 0.55 ± 0.19 for males) ($U=121.50$, $df=1$, $P= 0.02$) (Fig. 3b). However, the
292 mean number (NWEI) and the mean duration per event (WDE) of E1 and E2 were not
293 significantly different between sexes. Moreover, there was no difference for the duration
294 per event per insect (WDEI) for E1 or E2 between males and females of *B. trigonica*
295 (WDEI E1: 2.22 ± 0.90 for males and 3.23 ± 0.81 for females ($t=-0.78$, $df=1$, $P=0.41$) and
296 WDEI E2: 25.23 ± 10.94 for males and 45.07 ± 11.41 for females ($t=-1.25$, $df=1$, $P=0.22$)).
297 The proportion of individuals reaching phloem tissues at least once (PPW) was also not
298 different between males and females (8/20 males; 13/20 females) ($\chi^2=2.50$, $df=1$, $P=0.13$)
299 (Online resource 3). Further, other relevant phloem-related variables were significantly
300 higher for females than males. For example, the duration per insect for waveform D (WDI:
301 0.59 ± 0.24 for males and 1.72 ± 0.41 for females) ($U=123.50$, $df=1$, $P= 0.02$) and E2
302 (WDI: 15.14 ± 7.16 for males and 55.08 ± 16.14 for females) ($U=122.50$, $df=1$, $P= 0.02$)
303 were significantly higher for females than for males (Fig. 3c, e). Also, the number of single
304 E1 (NWEI: 0 for males and 0.3 ± 0.14 for females) ($U=160.00$, $df=1$, $P=0.03$) and the
305 number of sustained E2 (E2 events longer than 10 minutes) (NWEI: 0.25 ± 0.14 for males
306 and 0.75 ± 0.19 for females) ($U= 125.50$, $df=1$, $P= 0.01$) were higher for females than for
307 males (Fig. 3d, f).

308 **Discussion**

309 Most sex-specific responses of psyllids reported so far refer to settling and host selection
310 behaviour prior to probing and ingestion (Gharraei et al. 2014; Martini et al. 2015). Less
311 importance has been given to sex-specific probing behaviours associated with pathogen
312 transmission. Our work demonstrates that probing behaviour of male and female *B.*

313 *trigonica* differs in traits associated with inoculation of Lso. Although we found no
314 differences in the percentage of transmission between sexes, different probing behaviours
315 were correlated with differences in observed Lso transmission efficiency between males
316 and females.

317 Current experimental evidence suggests that Lso is transmitted in a propagative-circulative
318 manner, which means the bacteria replicate in their vectors and are inoculated in saliva
319 secreted before phloem ingestion (Sengoda et al. 2013; Cooper et al. 2014; Sandanayaka et
320 al. 2014; Mustafa et al. 2015; Cicero et al. 2016). Previous reports have shown that Lso
321 could be successfully inoculated in a single salivation event in a phloem sieve element by
322 *B. cockerelli* (Mustafa et al. 2015); Thus, it is likely that only small titres of bacteria
323 inoculated are needed to achieve infection. Therefore, similar proportions of males and
324 females reaching phloem sieve elements would lead to similar inoculation rates between
325 sexes as observed in our study. Our results are consistent with a previous study conducted
326 with *Bemisia tabaci* biotype B transmitting *Tomato yellow leaf curl virus* (TYLCV), where
327 similar percentage of males and females reached the phloem of tomato plants and caused
328 similar percentages of transmission of TYLCV for both sexes (Ning et al. 2015). In
329 addition, our data also agree with Nissinen et al. (2014), who reported similar Lso
330 percentages of transmission for male and females of the carrot psyllid *T. apicalis*.

331 On the other hand, the Lso titre in a psyllid body was positively correlated with Lso titre
332 inoculated into the plant. Despite the lack of differences in the mean values for Lso titre
333 inoculated between sexes, there was a significant interaction between sex and psyllid titer.
334 Hence, females with higher Lso titres tend to inoculate more bacteria into the plants than
335 males. This suggests that at high Lso titers, females might be more efficient at delivering

336 Lso than males. However, this result should be analysed carefully considering that our
337 sample size is small and larger data would be needed in order to give a stronger support to
338 our hypothesis. Different factors can affect the efficiency of pathogen inoculation. For
339 example, it is well known that the capacity to inoculate propagative-circulative pathogens
340 increases with higher phloem contacts as well as with longer salivation events (Jiang et al.
341 2000; Moreno-Delafuente et al. 2011; Mustafa et al. 2015). In our study, duration of psyllid
342 salivation in phloem sieve elements (E1) did not significantly differ between males and
343 females, but numerically were two times greater for females than for males. Also, females
344 showed a significantly higher frequency of phloem contacts, which is correlated with the
345 higher Lso transmission efficiency showed by females. Thus, it is likely that an increased
346 frequency of initial E1 as observed for females may play an important role explaining the
347 higher Lso transmission efficiency observed by females.

348 In addition to an increased frequency of phloem contacts, a higher number of sustained
349 phloem ingestion events as well as longer phloem ingestion events were observed for
350 females, suggesting that they ingest phloem sap more actively than males. These results are
351 consistent with related studies where increased phloem ingestion by females has been
352 observed in other psyllid species as well as other hemipterans such as whiteflies,
353 planthoppers, leafhoppers and thrips (Swenson et al. 1971; Narayana et al. 1996; Van de
354 Wetering et al. 1998; Serikawa 2011; Ning et al, 2015). Increased phloem ingestion could
355 be explained because females commonly require a high amount of nutrients to supply
356 energetically costly processes such as egg production (Swenson et al. 1971; Nissinen et al.
357 2014). As a result, this increased phloem ingestion would result in increased efficiency to
358 acquire a phloem-restricted pathogen such as Lso.

359 Previous studies have correlated symptom severity with Lso titre in potato and carrots
360 (Alvarado et al. 2012; Nissinen et al. 2014). In our study, symptom severity caused when
361 males or females transmitted Lso was similar except for the number of yellow leaves at a
362 psyllid density of eight. This lack of differences in symptoms using single psyllid densities
363 is consistent with the similar Lso titres inoculated by both sexes. Our results contrast with
364 Nissinen et al (2014), who reported more severe root damage when single females of *T.*
365 *apicalis* transmitted Lso compared to single males. Factors that may account for divergent
366 results between our study and Nissinen et al. (2014) may include differences in inoculation
367 efficiency between vector species, different inoculation access periods as well as different
368 plant varieties or genetic variants of the pathogen used.

369 On the other hand, our data revealed that Lso caused a greater number of yellow leaves
370 when inoculated by groups of eight females. We hypothesize that groups of psyllids
371 increase the Lso titre inoculated and could also synergize to magnify the differences
372 observed in inoculation efficiency between males and females. Thus, if females are more
373 efficient at inoculating Lso, it is expected that groups of females could inoculate higher
374 titres than males, explaining the differences in symptoms obtained. Actually, this
375 observation is consistent with previous studies that reported a positive correlation between
376 the number of yellow leaves and Lso titre (Nissinen et al. 2014), as well as with reports of
377 increased Lso titres inoculated by groups of four psyllids versus single ones (Rashed et al.
378 2012). Despite the supporting evidence, our hypothesis still requires further research to be
379 confirmed.

380 Finally, it is important to highlight that direct damage from psyllid feeding could have
381 contributed to the symptoms observed. However, because above-ground symptoms

382 appeared on average 40 days after psyllids were removed, we believe that they were caused
383 by Lso infection rather than by direct psyllid feeding as proposed by Nissinen et al. (2014).
384 However, discriminating between the effects of Lso and direct psyllid feeding on below-
385 ground symptoms is complicated because it has been reported that psyllid feeding could
386 affect root development in carrots (Nissinen et al. 2007). Thus, the possibility that part of
387 the root reduction observed could be due to direct psyllid feeding should not be completely
388 disregarded.

389 In summary, we can conclude that differences in probing behaviours observed between
390 males and females might impact the transmission of *Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*.
391 Further research is still needed in order to establish a direct relationship between symptom
392 severity and Lso titre in the plant. This study provides key information to understand the
393 transmission process of Lso mediated by its vector *B. trigonica*. Our results also highlight
394 the importance of taking psyllid sex into consideration for subsequent transmission or
395 probing behaviour studies.

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572 **Figures.**

573 **Figure 1.**

574 Percentage of Lso infected plants when Lso is transmitted by *Bactericera trigonica* males
575 or females at densities of one or eight psyllids per plant. Values represent the mean of three
576 different assays. Error bars represent standard error.

577 **Figure 2**

578 Analysis of psyllid vs receptor plant Lso titres. Y-axis values represent the Ln of Lso-
579 amplified targets per milligram of plant tissue and X-axis values represent three different
580 categories of psyllid titre (Low, Medium and High). Range of values for the Ln of Lso
581 amplified targets per psyllid in each category: Low=8.86 - 10.97, Medium =10.98 - 12.67,
582 High=12.68 - 15.33, each category contains eleven individuals. Error bars represent
583 standard error.

584 **Figure 3.**

585 Variables describing probing behaviours (Mean \pm SE) of males and females of *Bactericera*
586 *trigonica* on carrot plants. (a) Number (NWEI) of initial E1 (First salivation period in a
587 phloem probe); (b) Number (NWEI) of D (initial contact with phloem); (c) Duration (WDI)
588 of D (initial contact with phloem); (d) Number (NWEI) of Single E1 (salivation not
589 followed by phloem ingestion); (e) Duration (WDI) of E2 (phloem ingestion); (f) Number
590 (NWEI) of Sustained E2 (phloem ingestion longer than 10 minutes). Only the EPG
591 variables associated with phloem activities that showed significant differences are shown.
592 Information on all calculated variables is provided in online resource 3. NWEI = Mean

593 Number of Waveform Events per Insect. $WDI = \text{Mean Waveform Duration per Insect.}$

594 $WDE = \text{Mean Waveform Duration per Event.}$

595 # WDI and WDE are expressed in minutes.

596 *Significant differences according to Student's t-test (for Gaussian variables) or Mann-
597 Whitney U test (for non-Gaussian variables) ($P < 0.05$).

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614 **Figure 1**

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627 **Figure 2**

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637 **Figure 3**

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640 **Tables**641 **Table 1.**

642 Symptoms observed in carrot plants after the inoculation of Lso by single insects or groups of eight males or females of *Bactericera*
 643 *trigonica*. Root weight is represented in grams (g).

	one psyllid								eight psyllids							
	Root weight ¹	df	F	P*	Number of yellow leaves ²	df	H	P*	Root weight ²	df	H	P*	Number of yellow leaves ²	df	H	P*
Control	18.73 ± 1.34 a	2, 51	32.05	0.00	0.06 ± 0.06 a	2	12.49	0.00	17.16 ± 0.75 a	2	62.41	0.00	0.10 ± 0.45 a	2	78.97	0.00
Males	7.58 ± 1.04 b				0.85 ± 0.17b				9.39 ± 0.58 b				1.70 ± 0.19 b			
Females	6.06 ± 1.02 b				1.05 ± 0.26b				8.64 ± 0.66 b				2.80 ± 0.30 c			

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645 Letters indicate statistically significant differences between groups in columns (P<0.05) according to (1) One way factor ANOVA or

646 (2) Kruskal-Wallis test.

647 *P < 0.0001

648 **Table 2.**

649 Degrees of freedom (*df*) F-test (F) and significance (P) values for the comparison between
 650 the Lso titre inoculated by males or females of *B. trigonica* on carrots.

	<i>df</i>	F	Significance
Corrected model ⁺	5	6.45	0.01
Intercept	1	357.12	0.00*
Sex	1	2.78	0.10
Psyllid titre	2	13.93	0.00*
Sex*Psyllid titre	2	5.35	0.01
Error	26		
Total	32		

651 Dependent variable: Plant titre.

652 $R^2 = 0.55$ Adjusted $R^2 = 0.468$.

653 ⁺This term represents the overall effect of all main effects and interactions included in the
 654 model.

655 * $P < 0.0001$

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668 **Online resources**

669 Online resource 1.

670 Sequential and non-sequential EPG variables analyzed to compare the probing behaviours

671 of males and females of *B. trigonica* (Lso +) on carrot plants. Variables calculated

672 represent the mean values for each cohort of insects used in the study.

Non-sequential variables

Number of np

Number of Probes per Insect

Number of waveform events for C

Number of waveform events for E1

Number of waveform events for E2

Number of waveform events for G

Number of waveform events for D

Number of initial E1

Number of single E1

Number of single E2 > 10 min

Duration of np

Probing time

Waveform Duration per Insect for C

Waveform Duration per Insect for G

Waveform Duration per Insect for E1

Waveform Duration per Insect for E2

Waveform Duration per Insect for D

Waveform Duration per Event for C

Waveform Duration per Event for G

Waveform Duration per Event for E1

Waveform Duration per Event for E2

Waveform Duration per Event for D

Waveform Duration per Event per Insect for E1

Waveform Duration per Event per Insect for E2

Sequential variables

Total duration of E1 followed E2 sustained

Total duration of E1 followed E2

Time to 1st probe from start of EPG

Time from start of EPG to 1st E

Time from 1st probe to 1st E

Time from the beginning of that probe to 1st E

Time to from start of EPG 1st sustained E2 (10 minutes)

Time from 1st probe to 1st sustained E2 (10 minutes)

Time from the beginning of that probe to 1st sustained E2 (10 minutes)

Time from the beginning of that probe to 1st E2

Duration of np just after the probe of the first sustained E2 Number of probes after the 1st E1
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Online resource 2.

t-test comparison between the Lso titre inoculated in carrot plants by males and females with different quantities of Lso in insect body.

Psyllid titre	Levene's test		t-test for equality of means				
	F	Sig	t	df	sig (2 tailed)	Mean difference	Standart error
Low	0.25	0.62	-1.14	9	0.28	-1.17	1.03
Medium	1.00	0.34	1.59	9	0.14	1.93	1.21
High	0.67	0.43	-4.14	8	0.00	-3.74	0.90

Online resource 3.

Occurrence and duration (Mean \pm SE) of non-sequential DC-Electrical Penetration Graph (EPG) waveforms of *B. trigonica* (Lso +) carrot plants during an 8-h recording period. PPW, proportion of individuals that produced the waveform type; NWEI, number of waveform events per insect. WDI, waveform duration per insect (minutes). WDE, waveform duration per event. (minutes)

Non sequential variables	Psyllid gender	PPW	NWEI	P	WDI	P	WDE	P
Non probe	Male	20/20	11.90 \pm 1.72 (3-29)	0.04 ¹	205.82 \pm 22.71 (32.59-378.32)	0.31 ¹	17.29 \pm 2.37 (0.18-282.26)	0.01 ³
	Female	20/20	16.85 \pm 1.60 (7-39)		169.75 \pm 27.78 (33.97-431.43)		10.07 \pm 1.44 (0.11-316.63)	
Probes*	Male	20/20	11.45 \pm 1.71 (3-29)	0.04 ¹	271.16 \pm 22.49 (102.16 -447.40)	0.27 ¹	23.68 \pm 2.54 (0.21-308.60)	0.14 ¹
	Female	20/20	16.85 \pm 1.60 (7-39)		310.24 \pm 26.78 (48.55-446.01)		18.85 \pm 2.12 (0.15-292.01)	
C	Male	20/20	12.55 \pm 1.81 (3-30)	0.09 ¹	224.86 \pm 23.45 (55.93-400.86)	0.97 ¹	17.23 \pm 1.94 (0.7-308.60)	0.05 ²
	Female	20/20	16.85 \pm 1.68 (7-40)		226.08 \pm 23.65(55.93-410.01)		12.25 \pm 1.17 (0,3-214,46)	
D	Male	8/20	0.55 \pm 0.19 (0-3)	0.02 ³	0.59 \pm 0.24 (0-2.17)	0.02 ³	1.07 \pm 0.21 (0.37-2.64)	0.65 ¹
	Female	13/20	1.70 \pm 0.40 (0-6)		1.72 \pm 0.41 (0-3.11)		1.01 \pm 0.14 (0.31-4.92)	
E1	Male	7/20	1.35 \pm 0.47 (0-7)	0.10 ²	3.97 \pm 2.59 (0-50.73)	0.80 ³	3.45 \pm 0.99 (0.3-17.56)	0.89 ²
	Female	13/20	2.1 \pm 0.59 (0-10)		7.72 \pm 3.13 (0-57.45)		3.68 \pm 0.66 (0.1-18.77)	
E2	Male	7/20	1.15 \pm 0.39 (0-6)	0.10 ³	15.14 \pm 7.16 (0-98.78)	0.02 ³	15.14 \pm 5.86 (0.31-88.16)	0.22 ¹
	Female	13/20	1.75 \pm 0.46 (0-8)		55.08 \pm 16.14 (0-250.98)		31.47 \pm 9.50 (0.35-234.9)	
G	Male	20/20	1.45 \pm 0.13 (1-3)	0.03 ³	27.18 \pm 3.63 (5.71-87.48)	0.25 ²	18.74 \pm 3.02 (0.39-87.48)	0.16 ²
	Female	15/20	1 \pm 0.17 (0-3)		21.43 \pm 3.55 (0-48.82)		21.32 \pm 2.42 (1.14-48.82)	
Initial E1	Male	8/20	0.50 \pm 0.18 (0-3)	0.01 ³				
	Female	13/20	1.65 \pm 0.39 (0-6)					
Single E1	Male	0/20	0	0.03 ³				
	Female	4/20	0.3 \pm 0.14 (0-2)					
Sustained E2	Male	3/20	0.25 \pm 0.14 (0-2)	0.01 ³			52.60 \pm 13.49 (10.61-88.16)	0.57 ¹
	Female	11/20	0.75 \pm 0.19 (0-3)				71.09 \pm 17.77 (10.73-234.90)	

Waveforms: **C**, intercellular stylet pathway; **G**, xylem ingestion; **E** shows phloem-related activities: **E1**, correlates with salivation into phloem sieve elements; E2, ingestion from phloem (Prado and Tjallingii, 1994); **sE2**: sustained E2 (longer than 10 minutes) Single E1 refers to E1 not followed by E2. Initial E1 refers to E1 preceded by D waveform. Statistical comparisons for each variable were made by:

¹ t-Student for Gaussian distribution variables.

² t-Student for transformed variables.

³ Non-parametric U-Mann Whitney test for non-Gaussian distribution variables.

* Number of probes per insect (NPI)

Underlined values indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$)